

Original article

Vaginal hysterectomy at two tertiary hospitals in Maiduguri: a ten-year review of prevalence, trends, and outcomes.

Yakaka M. Tatabe,¹ Ado D. Geidam.²

¹Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, Borno State, Nigeria.

²Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

Corresponding author: Dr Yakaka Mustapha Tatabe, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, Borno State, Nigeria. Email: kktatabe@gmail.com Phone: +2347038363177.

Abstract

Background: Vaginal hysterectomy, though a major gynecological surgery commonly done for uterovaginal prolapse and other indications due to its advantages of short hospital stay, less morbidity, and quicker recovery time than abdominal hysterectomy, is not without a myriad of complications that may negatively impact women's lives. **Objective:** To review the prevalence, indication, trends, and outcome of vaginal hysterectomy in the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital and State Specialist Hospital, Maiduguri, Borno State. **Methodology:** A retrospective hospital-based descriptive study that reviewed all the vaginal hysterectomies done in the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH) and State Specialist Hospital, Maiduguri (SSHM) over ten years (January 2011 to December 2020). Patients' sociodemographic characteristics, indications, intraoperative findings, and complications were obtained and documented in a proforma design for the study. The data was analysed using SPSS version 25. The findings were presented as frequencies and percentages in tables. **Results:** The prevalence of vaginal hysterectomy (VH) in this study was 11.4%. Also, VH accounted for 17.4% of all hysterectomies done during the period. The mean age of the patient was 58 ± 11.1 years (range: 37–85), and the mean parity was 5 ± 2 (range: 2–13). Most of the patients, 42.0% (47/112), were married, while the commonest indication, 43.8% (49/112), was 4th-degree uterovaginal prolapse. The most common complication was intraoperative hemorrhage (14, 58.3%). **Conclusion:** Vaginal hysterectomy is safe, and the complications are few. Utero-vaginal prolapse was the commonest indication. Public enlightenment to prevent prolapse would reduce the incidence and the need for vaginal hysterectomy.

Keywords: 4th-degree prolapse, Intraoperative haemorrhage, SSHM, UMTH, Vaginal hysterectomy

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Introduction

Vaginal hysterectomy (VH) is among the major gynaecological surgeries in many centers. It involves surgical dissection and removal of the uterus via the vagina, with the approximation of the vacuum space created by the uterine removal with the lateral attachments of the vaginal vault.¹ It was first performed by Langenbeck in the year 1813, with subsequent modifications and improvements over the years.^{1,2}

The rate of VH reported in the United States of America was 21.8%,³ and rates of 30-40% were documented in France & Australia.^{4,5} Rates between 10.0% to 23% were reported from various studies in Nigeria.⁶⁻⁹

Pelvic organ prolapse is the commonest indication

of VH in most centres,^{6,8,9} however, other indications include cervical dysplasia, menorrhagia, dysfunctional uterine bleeding, and adenomyosis.

Tight vagina, invasive cancer of the cervix, uterine immobility, flushed cervix, and uterus of greater than 12 weeks are among the contraindications of VH in most gynaecological practices and guidelines.^{2,10}

Vaginal hysterectomy is done via natural orifice and has established advantages over abdominal hysterectomy that include decreased intraoperative blood loss, early return of bowel function, faster recovery, minimal scarring, shorter hospital stays, and reduced long-term complications such as adhesion, intestinal obstruction, and hernia.^{2,7,8,10}

Vaginal hysterectomy is also the preferred type of hysterectomy when pelvic floor repair is to be done.^{11,12} The complications of VH include hemorrhage, sepsis, and injury to nearby organs such as the bladder and rectum.^{6,11,13} This study aimed to determine the prevalence, indications, and outcomes of vaginal hysterectomy at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital and the State Specialist Hospital, Maiduguri, Borno State. The information obtained may be useful in counselling patients undergoing a hysterectomy.

Materials and methods

Study design

It was a hospital-based retrospective study that reviewed all the vaginal hysterectomies done in the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH) and State Specialist Hospital, Maiduguri (SSHM) over ten years (January 2011 to December 2020).

Study area

The study was a multicenter study conducted at the obstetrics and gynaecology departments of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH) and SSH Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

Ethical consideration

This study had ethical approval from the Ethical and Research Committees of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital and State Specialist Hospital, Maiduguri.

Data collection and analysis

Data collection was conducted simultaneously across the two hospitals by trained research assistants. The hospital numbers of all patients that underwent vaginal hysterectomy over the study period were obtained from the theatre and gynaecology ward registers of the two hospitals.

medical record department of the two hospitals. The sociodemographic data of the patients - age, occupation, marital status, and party; the indications; and the outcome of the vaginal hysterectomy - were extracted from the patients' case folders and entered into a pro forma design for the study. The data was analyzed using IBM SPSS version 25.0 software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the continuous data. Categorical data were presented in tables as frequencies and percentages.

The grading of uterovaginal prolapse in this study was based on the traditional clinical grading system routinely used in the participating hospitals.

Most of the hysterectomies (91.1%) were done by consultants, and (8.9%) were done by the senior registrar using standard techniques. The prevalence of vaginal hysterectomy was calculated as a percentage ratio of the total number of major gynaecological surgeries done during the study period and the rate of VH as a percentage ratio of the total number of hysterectomies (both vaginal and abdominal).

Intraoperative haemorrhage is defined as intraoperative blood loss of 500 ml and above. Visceral injury is when there is a recognized laceration or damage to other internal organs, like the bladder or bowel, requiring repair. Wound infection is the presence of abnormal vaginal discharge requiring antibiotic treatment, and febrile morbidity is a persistent temperature of 38°C and above.

Results

A total of 1282 major gynaecological operations were done across the 2 tertiary hospitals.

during the study period. Hysterectomy accounted for 838, of which 146 (17.4%) of

These were vaginal hysterectomies (VH). The prevalence rate of VH was 11.4%.

The rate of vaginal hysterectomy in the State Specialist Hospital, Maiduguri, and University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH) was 18.6% and 9.4%, respectively.

Of the 146 VH cases, 112 of the retrieved folders (76.7%) had complete records.

and were analyzed.

These were used to retrieve the case files from the

Table 1: Distribution of major Gynaecological procedures, total hysterectomies, and vaginal hysterectomies in the two study hospitals

HOSPITAL	TOTAL GYNAECOLOGICAL PROCEDURES	TOTAL HYSTERECTOMY	VAGINAL HYSTERECTOMY	VH RATE (%)
State Specialist Hospital Maiduguri	882	731	136	18.6
University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital	400	107	10	9.4
Total	1282	838	146	17.4

The flow chart for the cases is presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Consort flow chart of the reviewed case**Table 2. Sociodemographic characteristics of the study population**

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Parity		
0-4	41	36.6
5-7	48	42.8
8-10	18	16.0
11-13	5	4.6
Total	112	100
Occupation		
Unemployed housewife	50	44.6
Civil servant	25	22.3
Businesswoman	19	17.0
Artisan	18	16.1
Total	112	100
Marital status		
Married	47	42.0
Widowed	38	33.9
Divorced	27	24.1
Total	112	100
Age		
<50	23	20.4
50-69	68	60.9
>=70	21	18.7
Total	112	100

The demographic characteristics of the study population are shown in Table 2. Most of the patients, 42.0% (47/112), were married, and 50% (50/112) were housewives. Most of the patients, 38 (34.1%), were within the age range of 50–59 years, with only 3 (2.6%) patients within the age range of 30–39 years. The mean age was 58 ± 11.1 , and the mean parity was 5 ± 2 (range: 2–13). All the patients were multiparous.

Table 3: Indication of the vaginal hysterectomy in the study population

Indication	Frequency	Percentage
2 nd degree prolapses	15	13.4
3 rd degree prolapses	45	40.2
4 th degree prolapses	49	43.8
Cervical dysplasia	3	2.6
Total	112	100

Table 3 shows the indications of vaginal hysterectomy in the study population. Most of the procedures, 43.8% (49/112), were done because of 4th-degree uterovaginal prolapse, and in 2.6% (3/112), the indication was cervical dysplasia.

Fig 2. Yearly trend of vaginal hysterectomy

The yearly rate of VH is shown in Figure 2. There was no recognizable trend. The highest rate was 18.1% in 2018, and the lowest rate (5%) was in 2016.

Table 4. The complication of vaginal hysterectomy in study patients

Complications	Frequency	Percentage
Intraoperative haemorrhage	14	58.3
Postoperative haemorrhage	5	20.8
Anaemia	2	8.3
Visceral injury	1	4.2
Urinary tract infection	1	4.2
Febrile morbidity	1	4.2
Total	24	100

Of the total 112 vaginal hysterectomies performed during the study period, 24 developed complications, a complication rate of 21.4%. (Some had more than one complication). There was no

mortality recorded. The most common complications recorded were intraoperative haemorrhage 14, 58.3%), and the least common complication is seen in visceral injury, urinary tract infection, and febrile morbidity 1(4.2%), respectively. This was shown in Table 4.

Discussion

The mean age of the patients in this study was 58 ± 11.1 . This was like the reports of another study 9 but higher than those reported by Bukar et al⁷ and J. A. Obuna et al.¹⁴. The mean parity of 5 ± 2 was probably a reflection of this age. Repeated pregnancies cause injuries to the pelvic floor, and old age leads to degenerative changes and depletion of estrogen, causing a decrease in endopelvic fascia support and genital prolapse that may require VH. Also, women 40 years and above probably have completed their family size and/or are perimenopausal and are likely to choose vaginal hysterectomy as a management option when they develop pelvic organ prolapse.

The total number of gynaecological operations was

used as the denominator in calculating prevalence in this study, and the prevalence of VH of 11.4% (133.9/1000)

found in this study is like the prevalence of 10.7% reported by Bukar et al,⁷ higher than the 3% reported in Jos⁷ and the 2.3%¹⁵ reported in Enugu. However, our rate of VH (ratio of VH to the total hysterectomies) of 17.4 % was like that of a study done in Nguru (15.1 %),¹³ but lower than the rate of 45.7 % reported by a study in Abakaliki.¹⁴ A lower rate of 3 %⁹ was reported from Jos. These variations may be explained by the varied institutional and personal preferences of abdominal hysterectomy or vaginal hysterectomy.¹³

The commonest indication of VH in this study was 4th-degree prolapse, which conflicts with a study done in Abakaliki⁴ which showed 3rd-degree prolapse to be the commonest indication. This may probably be due to the differing health-seeking behaviour of the study populations, with women in Abakaliki being more likely to present earlier than women in our environment. Also, our cultural values are such that women hardly report anything pudendal until the condition is unbearable, like it is with the 4th- degree prolapse.

The yearly rate of VH during the study period did not reveal any trend, most likely because of the disruptions of services due to the various industrial actions by health workers during the study period.

The complication rate of VH of 21.4% recorded in this study was similar to those of other studies done in the country,^{9,13} but lower than that reported from Gombe.⁷ This lower rate could be because of the cadre of the surgeons that did the operation, as more than 90% of the operations in this study were performed by a consultant, compared to the Gombe study, where about a quarter of the procedures were performed by residents.

The common complications of major surgeries include risk of haemorrhage and infection, and in our study, the commonest complication recorded was haemorrhage (intraoperative haemorrhage and postoperative haemorrhage). This was similar to the report of the study from Nguru¹³ but in contrast, the studies from Gombe⁷ and Jos⁹ reported infection to be the commonest complication. Haemorrhage is common after vaginal hysterectomy¹⁶ because the pelvis is very rich in blood supply, and also because of the difficulty in visualizing and ligating major and minor blood vessels due to the nature of the operative field.

Limitations of the study

This is a hospital-based study and may not be representative of the wider population. The retrospective design of this study is prone to

selection bias, and some case notes could not be retrieved, and some did not have complete information.

Conclusion and recommendations

This study shows that vaginal hysterectomy is not uncommon in our practice, with the commonest indication being 4th-degree prolapse and the mean age of the patients being 58 ±1. Haemorrhage is the commonest complication encountered.

There is a need to reduce the prevalence of pelvic organ prolapse through public enlightenment and community mobilization. Attention should be given to haemostasis during VH. There is a need for an analytical study to explore the possible determinants of morbidity in VH.

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